

DEFORMATION OF GRAPHENE SHEETS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the issue of warping of graphene sheets in a suspended state. Various mechanisms for the formation of corrugations, wrinkles and folds on graphene sheets have been proposed. A new model of graphene warping has been proposed. Its essence lies in the fact that graphene is obtained, in most cases, from graphite, where significant internal stresses are present, and in the graphite nanolayer all physical (thermal, etc.) and chemical (adsorption, etc.) parameters of graphene change.

Keywords: graphite; graphene; nanolayer; mesolayer; warping.

Introduction

Graphene, discovered 20 years ago [1-2], is an amazing material used in various fields of human activity (Fig. 1) [3-5]. Today, the global graphene market is only just forming (Figure 2a) and is represented by companies in various countries (Figure 2b), where China and the USA are leaders. The methods for obtaining graphene are quite diverse. They are reviewed

in [2-5]. In [7-9], an original innovative method for obtaining graphene using microcluster water in combination with ultrasound and an electric field is proposed.

However, it is not possible to obtain large-sized graphene due to the warping of graphene sheets.

Figure 1. Graphene and its applications [6].

Global Graphene Market Dynamics in Million USD

(Source: Grand View Research)

The purpose of this article is to review previous work on graphene warping and propose a mechanism for developing this process.

Review of previous works

In [10], individual graphene sheets suspended freely on a microframe in vacuum or air were studied. The results demonstrate internal microscopic roughness, such that the surface normal varies by several degrees, and out-of-plane deformations reach 1 nm.

Figure 3a shows a bright-field TEM image of a suspended graphene membrane. Its central part (the homogeneous and featureless region indicated by arrows) is a monolayer graphene. Electron diffraction images

from different parts of the flake show that this is a single crystal without domains. The work notes the twisted upper and lower edges of the graphene. Warping (the appearance of elastic corrugations) of the graphene sheets is noted, which is associated with the high mobility of charge carriers in graphene.

Theoretical calculation of this warping of graphene sheets using the Monte Carlo method showed [11] that the ripples (corrugations) (Figure 3b) spontaneously appear due to thermal fluctuations with a size distribution peaking at about 80 Å, which is compatible with the conclusions (50-100 Å) of [10].

Figure 3. Suspended graphene membrane (a) [10]; sample configuration $N = 8640$ at $T = 300$ K. Red arrows have a length of ~ 80 Å (b) [11]

However, the conclusions of [11] were criticized in [12], where it was theoretically shown that edge stresses introduce internal ripples (warping) into free-

standing graphene sheets [10] even in the absence of any thermal effects (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Shapes of deformed graphene sheets [12]

A review [13] describes various mechanisms of wrinkle, ripple and fold formation (Figure 5), as well as the interaction between wrinkle and ripple attributes (wavelength/width, amplitude/height, length/size and

bending radius) and the electronic properties of graphene and other mechanical, optical, surface and chemical properties.

Figure 5. Corrugated (a), wrinkled (b) and crumpled (c) graphene [13]

In the review [13], various mechanisms of wrinkle, ripple and wrinkling formation in graphene are described, such as (a) thermal vibrations of the two-dimensional lattice, (b) edge instability, defects and dislocations, (c) negative thermal expansion (in contrast to positive thermal expansion for the substrate); (d) evaporation/removal of the trapped solvent, (e) relaxation of the prestrained substrate, (f) anchoring on the substrate, (g) surface potential of the substrate and (h) surface tension of the solvent. The deformation of graphene is controlled by its mechanical properties (Young's modulus, interfacial energy and number of layers), and the resulting corrugations change its electronic structure (opening of the band gap (potentially > 1 eV), pseudomagnetic field in bilayers, formation of electron-hole puddles and charge carrier transport). These, in turn, can be used to modify graphene's wettability, transmittance, chemical potential, expansion for energy storage, and conductivity. In the near future, it is important to (a) control the physical properties of these corrugations; (b) carefully study the effects of the ripples on the electronic, optical, mechanical, and chemical properties; and (c) study these effects on other 2D nanomaterials.

In [14], molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed to study the effect of ripples on the Poisson's ratio of graphene. Due to the atomic-scale thickness of graphene, out-of-plane ripples are generated in free-standing graphene with topological defects (e.g., heptagons and pentagons) to release in-plane strain energy. Using MD simulations, it was found that the Poisson's ratio of rippled graphene decreases with increasing its aspect ratio η (wavelength amplitude). For the rippled graphene sheet with $\eta = 0.188$, a negative Poisson's ratio of 0.38 is observed for a tensile strain of up to 8%, while the Poisson's ratio for $\eta = 0.066$ is almost zero. Under uniaxial tension, the ripples gradually become flat, so the Poisson's ratio of the rippled graphene is determined by the competing factors of the intrinsic positive Poisson's ratio of graphene and the negative Poisson's ratio due to the wrinkle-smoothing effect. In addition, the rippled graphene exhibits excellent tensile strength and toughness. Due to the combination of its acoustic and excellent mechanical properties, the rippled graphene may have potential for applications in nanodevices and nanomaterials. Illustrations of five rippled graphene sheets are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Illustrations of five corrugated graphene sheets with aspect ratios $\eta = (h/l) = 0.066$ (a), $\eta = 0.086$ (b), $\eta = 0.116$ (c), $\eta = 0.166$ (d), $\eta = 0.188$ (e)

In Figure 6, heptagonal and pentagonal defects are marked in red and blue. (f) Side view $\eta = 0.188$, where h is the amplitude and l is the wavelength.

We note the latest work [15] on graphene on a similar issue. Using the MD method, the features of the deformation behavior and the process of destruction of graphene containing dislocation dipoles with different shoulders were analyzed. Warping of graphene during deformation was taken into account, which greatly reduces its strength.

It was found that an increase in temperature has little effect on the mechanical properties of graphene

with dislocation dipoles, in contrast to defect-free graphene and graphene with a Stone-Wales defect. It was shown that a change in the distance between dislocations in a dipole does not have a noticeable effect on the elastic modulus and strength of graphene, however, the presence of dislocation dipoles can affect the warping of graphene during stretching.

Our model

Let's turn to our model. Let's start with graphite, which is an allotropic modification of carbon (Figure 7a). If you split off one monolayer from graphite, you get graphene (Figure 7b).

Figure 7. Crystal structure of graphite (a) and graphene (b)

In works [16-17] for the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ of a solid (including graphite) the formula was obtained:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu \text{ (m)}. \quad (1)$$

The model is shown schematically in Figure 8a. Equation (1) shows that the thickness of the surface

layer $R(I)$ is determined by one parameter – the molar (atomic) volume of the element ($\nu = M/\rho$, M is the molar mass (kg/mol), ρ is the density (kg/m³)), which periodically changes in accordance with the table of D. I. Mendeleev (Figure 8b).

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the surface layer (a), periodic change in the atomic volume of elements (b)

The parameters of graphite and graphene are given in Table 1. In Table 1: T_m is the melting temperature; γ is the surface energy (surface tension) on the a and c faces.

Table 1.

Parameters of graphite and graphene						
Carbon	ρ , g/sm ³	T_m , K	$R(I)_a$, nm	$R(I)_c$, HM	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
Graphite	2,26	3970	0,90 (3)	2,46 (3)	2779	591
Graphene	2,23	4510	0,246 (1)	0,14 (1)	3157	-

In work [18] it is shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 with an accuracy of up to 3% is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K). In the R(I) layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy of the R(I) layer becomes equal to γ_1 [19]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase boundary, which is negligibly small due to the second-order phase transition.

To separate the R(I) layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the adhesion energy [20]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2. \quad (4)$$

Internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 can be calculated using the formula [20]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \tilde{L}/R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of elasticity.

Using equations (1) - (5), we calculate the elastic parameters for graphite and graphene (table 2). In [21], it is shown that even small deformations of graphene within 10% are sufficient for warping of its surface

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite and graphene						
Carbon	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , GPa	σ_{isc} , GPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
Graphite	2,853	1,690	4,9	1,36	7,59	3,48
Graphene	3,448	-	118,4	-	1000	-

Significant internal stresses σ_{isa} in graphene definitely lead to warping of graphene sheets. If in Table 2 we take $\sigma_{isa} = 118.4$ GPa for 100% for graphene, and $\sigma_{isa} = 4.9$ GPa for x% for graphite, then during the formation of graphene we will obtain a graphene deformation of 4%, which is slightly lower than the mentioned 10%.

The work [22] can be cited on the warping of the graphene surface due to internal stresses. It shows an AFM image of the graphene surface, from which it is

evident that the surface consists of domains measuring 20 x 50 nm, oriented in one direction and forming "folds" on the graphene surface with a height of 1 nm (see the work [10] above). In this case, the roughness value on an area of 0.5 x 0.5 μm is $R_a = 0.25$ nm.

In Table 1, the number of monolayers $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the lattice constant) is given in brackets; for graphite $n = 3$, for graphene $n = 1$. Thus, graphite has three monolayers, which are confirmed in [23, 24] (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Change in atomic voltage (red line) and maximum average pressure (green line) depending on the number of graphene layers (a) [23]; dependence of the thermal conductivity coefficient of films composed of several graphene layers on their number (b) [24]

Both figures clearly show that the R(I) layer for graphite contains three layers, which indicates the validity of model (1). More than three layers of graphene transform into graphite and the values of the quantities in Figure 9 cease to depend on the number of layers.

The first monolayer of graphite - graphene, has strong covalent σ -bonds C-C in the plane of the graphene sheet in combination with π -electrons outside it determines the unique physicochemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific surface area ($\sim 2600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), high mobility of charge carriers ($\sim 200,000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$), high Young's modulus ($\sim 1000 \text{ GPa}$), thermal conductivity ($\sim 5000 \text{ W/m K}$), optical transparency ($\sim 97.7\%$), mechanical strength, etc. [1-5].

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite. It is actively studied [25] due to its controlled band gap. The analogue of bilayer graphene is Stone-Wales graphene or SW graphene, which is more stable in structure than graphene [26]. Three-layer graphene differs from the latter two in its mobility and conductivity [27]. After its magic angle twisting, it develops superconductivity, which withstands magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [28]. The following equations follow from equation (1) and Figure 8a [16]:

$$A(r) = A_0 \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{r} \right), \quad R(I) < r < R(II) \quad (6)$$

$$A(r) = A_0 \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + r} \right), \quad 0 < r < R(I),$$

where $A(r)$ is a property of the nano- and mesolayer; A_0 is a property of the volume; $r = z$ (Figure 8a).

The size effects in the R(I) layer are determined by the entire collective of atoms in the system (collective processes). Such size effects are observed only in nanoparticles and nanostructures [29]. In the nanostructured R(I) layer with solid atoms, reconstruction or relaxation occurs, associated with the restructuring of the surface [30]. This is one of the variants of graphene warping. The R(I) surface layer is a synergetic system, the fundamental properties of which are subject to self-regulation and self-organization. At $h = R(I)$, a second-order phase transition (according to Ehrenfest) occurs, where a jump in heat capacity occurs (Figure 8a). We considered this effect in [31]. The R(II) layer, which we will call the mesostructure (Figure 5a), extends to approximately the size $h \approx 9 R(I)$, where the bulk phase begins. From this size ($< 9 R(I)$) size effects of a different type begin. The difference between mesostructures and nanostructures and the bulk phase is that only in these systems are flicker noises with a spectrum of the $1/f_b$ type observed [32]. In the R(II) layer, there should be many size effects associated with temperature [33], magnetism [34], optics [35], and other properties. In the R(I) nanolayer, all its physical parameters change, including the graphene monolayer. They lead to a violation of the basic laws, in particular, to a violation of the Wiedemann-Franz law (Figure 10) [36]. If we take the Lorentz number $L(h)$ included in equation (6) as the physical property $A(h)$, then at $1 - R(I)/R(I) + h \approx \exp[-(R(I)/R(I) + h)]$ in the nanolayer it will be $= L_0/\exp[-(R(I)/R(I) + h)]$. After this, the Lorentz number, that is, at $h = 0$ and at $h = R(I)$ will be equal to: $L(h=0) = L_0/e$; $L[h = R(I)] = L_0/e^{0.5}$. The Lorentz number decreases on the metal surface by 2.72 times, and at the boundary of the R(I) layer – by 1.65 times. All this is shown in Figure 10a. In the mesolayer, the Lorentz number will depend on formula 1 in equation (6), while $1 - R(I) \approx \exp(-R(I)/h)$. Then $L[R(I)/9R(I)] = L_0 (1/e^{0.9}) \approx L_0$ and the Lorentz number will look like in Figure 10b.

Figure 10. Lorentz number in the nanolayer (a) and in the mesolayer (b) [36]

Figure 10a shows that the Lorentz number in the nanolayer $R(I)$ decreases in a stepwise manner, proving its quantum structure.

Large graphene sheets have only been obtained by depositing it on pure copper and nickel foils [3-4]. If we take into account that according to formula (1): for copper $R(I) = 1.2$ (3) nm; for nickel $R(I) = 1.1$ (3) nm and compare these values with those indicated in Table 1, then the conclusion follows that they have close $R(I)$ values and also contain three nanolayers. This correspondence opens the way to creating larger graphene sizes, which is relevant for surface engineering of this amazing material.

Conclusion

Thus, the warping of graphene sheets is due to the fact that it is obtained, in most cases, from graphite, where significant internal stresses are present, and in the graphite nanolayer all physical (thermal, etc.) and chemical (adsorption, etc.) parameters of graphene change.

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